

AUTONOMIC BIOMOLECULAR MATERIAL SYSTEMS AS MULTIFUNCTIONAL COMPOSITES

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1 Abstract

Nature has created a vast array of stimuli-responsive materials that support basic life function. Many of these materials are composites since their properties and function are derived from multiple types of constituent materials. The basic building block of these natural materials is the cell, and it is interesting to consider the fact that the diversity of function in many biological materials is derived from the aggregation of fundamental processes at the cellular level. Processes such as charge and mass transport across semipermeable boundaries plays a key role in natural processes such as sensing, actuation, metabolic control, and the growth of biological systems, and that these processes have been exhibited in single-celled and multicellular organisms since the beginning of life on this planet.

Our group has recently initiated a program to understand how we can utilize biomolecules to create a new class of autonomic biomolecular material that exhibits multifunctional behavior. Specifically, we are studying how to incorporate ion channels into durable material systems to enable multifunctional behavior that mimics that of biological materials and systems. There are fundamental challenges in understanding how biomolecules such as ion channels can self-assemble into interfacial bilayers incorporated in synthetic materials; how to model their function across six orders of magnitude in length scale to design engineered biomolecular materials; and to develop new methods of fabricating materials with sufficient functional density to enable multifunctional, autonomic behavior.

2 The Biomolecular Unit Cell

Our material concept is based upon a unit cell that enables the incorporation of stimuli-responsive biomolecules. As shown in Figure 1, the critical element of this unit cell is a nanometer-thick lipid bilayer that is formed at the interface of two

Figure 1: Biomolecular unit cell as a basis for studying the function of autonomic materials.

compartments that have hydrophilic properties. In the original embodiment of this concept, these compartments were aqueous electrolytes but more recent work has demonstrated that hydrated gels can be utilized as well without hindering bilayer formation or biomolecular function [1].

The diversity of biomolecules allows the introduction of different types of stimuli-responsive functionalities. Previous work has demonstrated the incorporation of light-activated ion channels at the bilayer interface. Our group has demonstrated the ability to incorporate pores into the membrane, voltage-gated ion channels, as well as light-activated molecules [2]. We have demonstrated the ability to measure macroscopic changes in conductance, capacitance, and luminescence due to the incorporation of stimuli-responsive biomolecules.

2.1 Mechanosensitive channels as a model system

Our current initiative will utilize the mechanosensitive channels of large conductance (MscL) as a model system in a detailed study of biomolecular material systems. The ion channel

Figure 2: Biomolecular material system concept based on the stimuli-responsive properties of known ion channels.

MscL was first identified in prokaryotes by Martinac, et al, and cloned by Sukharev, et al [3,4]. Since that time the stimuli-responsive mechanisms within the channel have been identified, resulting in an understanding of the relationship between surface tension within the membrane and channel activation. At the outset our program will focus on a fundamental understanding of dynamic surface tension in the membrane and channel activity; a physical understanding of ion channel insertion and self-assembly; and the effect of surface tension relaxation on sensing response of the ion channel.

3 System Concept

Figure 2 illustrates a broader concept for the development of autonomic biomolecular material systems. We envision utilizing the diversity of coupling mechanisms in biological molecules to create materials and material systems that exhibit new sensing, actuation, and energy conversion modalities. Of particular interest is a fundamental understanding of how the discrete changes in channel conductance lead to novel transduction modalities.

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